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Prospects of the International North–South Transport Corridor in the Context of Economic Integration Projects of the EAEU

KEYWORDS

Eurasian transport policy, highway, railway communication, logistics route, North–South transport corridor, economic integration project

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) is actively integrating into the system of international transport corridors by forming its own network of Eurasian routes. Future expansion of participation in the North–South Transport Corridor (NSTC) by all member states of the EAEU is anticipated.

The study is aimed at analyzing the prospects of NSTC within the context of the EAEU's economic integration projects.

Materials and methods. The study utilized online publications, scientific articles, and regulatory legal documents pertaining to the development of the EAEU's transport infrastructure. Research methods included modeling, analysis of the interrelationship between infrastructure projects and trade-economic indicators, and visualization of routes and cargo flows.

Results. Main international transport corridors traverse the territories of the member states, such as the Pan-European, Trans-Caspian, and Central Asian routes, among others, which provide connectivity between Europe, Asia, and the Pacific region. A coordinated transport policy is being implemented under the EAEU's legal framework, aimed at establishing a unified transport space, developing transit potential, infrastructure, and logistics centers. A comprehensive plan for the development of transport corridors for the short and long term was formulated in 2023. Particular emphasis is placed on highway quality standards, their safety, and the provision of necessary services.

Conclusion. The prospects for the NSTC within the EAEU's economic integration projects are tied to its potential to become a key transport and logistics link within the Union. The realization of this corridor facilitates the strengthening of economic integration, infrastructure optimization, and a reduction in transport costs, which positively impacts foreign trade, investment attraction, and the development of joint projects. In the context of geopolitical shifts, the NSTC can play a significant role in bolstering economic stability, diversifying trade routes, and expanding cooperation in transport, logistics, and infrastructure among the EAEU member states.

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INTRODUCTION

International economic relations cannot develop without the involvement of natural and labor resources of individual states into interstate trade and economic cooperation to ensure their national and economic security. One of the factors determining the competitiveness of economies operating within the global economic system is the level of transport and logistics development and their integration into the worldwide transport system. In this regard, it is of paramount importance to identify the trends emerging in the transport sector across the Eurasian space, which directly impact the international transit of goods and vehicles across the borders of neighboring states.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The North–South Transport Corridor (NSTC) possesses a number of advantages and significant potential: strategic geographical location; enhancement of trade links; stimulation of economic growth; infrastructure development; and potential for integration with other international routes.

L. Vydashenko and P. Vydashenko note that the NSTC, which begins in St. Petersburg and terminates at the port of Mumbai (India), is designed to improve logistics between the Russian Federation and the countries of the Persian Gulf and South Asia. According to the researchers, this route will allow for the restoration of parts of transport chains and an increase in cargo turnover, even considering the restrictions and sanctions imposed by the US and the EU [1].

A. Gevorgyan states that, from an economic perspective, the corridor serves as a catalyst for trade and commerce growth. It facilitates the efficient movement of goods between participating countries, connects various economic zones, reduces transportation costs and time, thereby providing a significant impetus to regional economic development [2].

E. Vinokurov et al. argue that the main advantage of the NSTC over other transport routes is the substantial reduction in cargo delivery times. The researchers estimate the NSTC's freight potential to be between 14.6 and 24.7 million tons per year. In the long term, the transport corridor could evolve into an economic development corridor for the EAEU countries by fostering industrial cooperation and establishing logistics chains with countries gravitating towards the NSTC [3].

P. Babu et al. indicate that the NSTC has significantly reduced the time and cost of freight transportation between these regions, leading to an increase in the volume and value of trade. According to the authors, the NSTC has had a positive impact on international trade between India, Russia, and Europe and has contributed to economic growth and development in the region [4].

E. V. Pak and P. O. Korolev provide a critical assessment of the potential and key challenges of the NSTC, taking into account significant changes in global supply chains caused by recent Western sanctions against the Russian Federation. In the researchers' view, this route holds considerable potential, given the reorientation of trade flows from and to Russia that has been observed since the beginning of 2022 [5].

A. Krylatov et al. demonstrate that with a projected freight demand between St. Petersburg and Mumbai reaching 41 million tons per year by 2030, transit time between Europe and Asia via the NSTC could be reduced by 20–40% compared to existing routes. According to the researchers, further investment in border crossings and transshipment hubs could increase capacity by over 100 million tons, solidifying the corridor's position as a viable alternative for routes connecting Asia, Europe, India, and North America [6].

E. A. Mamaev and D. V. Sorokin assess the potential for the transport corridor's development and the enhancement of its appeal through the use of multimodal transport schemes to attract cargo flows (including exports) from adjacent routes. The authors examine the prospects for the NSTC's development, which depend on geopolitical and infrastructural (technological) factors. The technological factor is linked to challenges within Russia's transport system, such as infrastructure congestion on the approaches to the ports of the Azov-Black Sea basin, the Moscow-Krasnodar railway line, and others, which directly impact the corridor's potential [7].

The development prospects for the NSTC include the expansion of transport routes, infrastructure modernization, increased cargo flow, and the strengthening of international ties, all of which contribute to economic growth and regional integration.

S. Luzyanin analyzes the key transport, economic, and international political aspects of the NSTC project, including its domestic Russian dimensions and the specific contexts of the South Caucasus (Azerbaijan, Armenia), the Caspian region (Iran), India, and China. The study explores opportunities for optimization and potential avenues for Russia's further regional integration on the Eurasian continent [8].

R. V. Fedorenko identifies the prospects for the NSTC's development and outlines the most important trends in improving its customs and logistics infrastructure. The

scholar highlights the main problems hindering the full utilization of the corridor's transit potential and identifies trends for enhancing its transport, customs, and logistics infrastructure [9].

P. Kurenkov et al. consider the NSTC development in the context of internationally coordinated construction of transport, customs, and border infrastructure facilities. This aims to ensure the integration of Euro-Asian transport systems and enhance the competitiveness of Russian manufacturers and enterprises [10].

M. Malyshev and E. Kozhanov argue that the problems of developing the NSTC are directly related to the integration of regional infrastructure among the countries participating in the project. The authors propose the following pathways to maximize the NSTC's potential and increase its competitiveness: modernization of infrastructure; comprehensive digitalization of the transport and logistics sector in all participating countries; and harmonization of the institutional conditions for the project's implementation in the areas of legislation, customs procedures, business processes, and management [11].

M. Lelyavina and A. Kuldorov analyze the prospects for the development of the Southern Federal District as one of the strategic directions of an emerging center for transnational trade and a crucial transport hub within the NSTC system. This aims to enhance food security and develop the agro-industrial complex. The scholars assess the efficiency of using cargo transportation through the Southern Federal District via the NSTC as an alternative to the Southern Sea Route [12].

Interaction among the NSTC participant countries is based on cooperation in transport, logistics, and infrastructure, information exchange, and joint projects aimed at improving route efficiency and strengthening economic ties.

N. Aliyev examines the interests, expectations, challenges, and benefits of the respective participants in the NSTC. The scholar explores how the geopolitical and geo-economic interests of the NSTC member states either compete or align concerning this corridor, and identifies specific areas where the corridor is influenced by these competing or converging interests [13].

S. Lunev and V. Belov analyze the potential of the emerging strategic partnership relations between India and Iran. The authors demonstrate that one of the main features of India's foreign policy – balancing – is also evident in its relations with Iran, which has been under Western sanctions for decades [14].

L. Pal believes that this project will foster the development of bilateral relations among the participating countries. India will gain easy access to the resource-rich countries of Central Asia via this corridor, bypassing Pakistan. It will help India export its goods to countries in Northern and Central Asia, including Russia, and import hydrocarbons at a lower cost, avoiding the traditional long route. In the near future, it is poised to fundamentally reshape India's policy in Eurasia [15].

A. Keliwaal and A. Mubariz explore Afghanistan's opportunities within the NSTC. The scholars emphasize the importance of utilizing the NSTC for Afghanistan's economic development and its role in regional integration. Afghanistan can leverage its strategic location to become a significant transit hub, facilitating trade between Europe, Central Asia, and the Indian Ocean region [16].

H. Noorali and S. A. Ahmadi note that Iran occupies a unique geographical position, acting as a bridge between Africa, Europe, and Asia, connecting India and Russia within the NSTC, among others. Iran has been identified as one of the world's most critical geographical nodal points, playing a combination of geopolitical, geo-economic, and geo-transit roles in Southwest Asia [17].

D. Giang notes that Russia and Azerbaijan have implemented several specific cooperation measures to facilitate the project's implementation. Cooperation between Russia and Azerbaijan has yielded numerous positive results, including the establishment of a legal framework, the modernization of infrastructure, and a noticeable increase in trade [18].

A. Beifert and A. Moldabekova argue that the significance of the Trans-Eurasian transport corridor, particularly the segment crossing the Caspian Sea, has increased substantially. The ports of the Caspian Sea, besides forming crucial transport hubs and providing access for landlocked countries of Central Asia and the Caucasus, play a vital role in the global supply chain. They offer essential infrastructure, logistics services, and connectivity to ensure the seamless transshipment of cargo from sea to land transport, thereby enhancing the efficiency of trade flows along the Eurasian Transport Corridor. The scholars assess the overall readiness of logistics services in the Caspian Sea ports based on statistical and empirical data obtained from a study of the port of Aktau [19].

The peculiarities of NSTC development in the Russian section include the modernization of infrastructure, integration of transport systems, improvement of logistics, and expansion of cargo flow, all of which contribute to strengthening the region's economic potential.

V. Vereskun et al. conduct a predictive analysis of the freight turnover dynamics within the transport corridor, identifying the drivers and barriers to its development amid changing geopolitical and economic market conditions. The authors demonstrate that rail transport within the Russian section of the NSTC is becoming a key factor for development and enhancing the competitiveness of shipments compared to alternative routes [20].

L. Kazanskaya and M. Chetchuev have developed a methodology for economic assessment of return on investment in the development of the NSTC infrastructure. The researchers proposed indicators and algorithms for calculating transport and non-transport effects, and estimated the payback periods for investments by the Russian side (Russian investors) in the NSTC infrastructure [21].

L. Vydashenko analyzes the current state of construction of the western bypass of the Saratov railway junction. An essential task in organizing the Saratov bypass is its implementation as part of the NSTC [22].

E. Kryukova notes that Russian special economic zones do not form a cohesive network but rather represent isolated, innovation-oriented elements within the economic space of Russia's low-technology economy. The scholar provides an analysis of three route options for the NSTC: freight transportation by rail, the western branch, and the eastern branch [23].

Thus, the analysis of literature analyzes the NSTC. Studies indicate that this route facilitates the restoration of supply chains, increases cargo turnover, and reduces delivery times, thereby stimulating trade and economic growth in the region. Significant advantages include reduced transportation costs and time, as well as the potential for developing industrial cooperation and logistics chains. However, challenges related to infrastructure and geopolitical issues, such as sanctions and shifts in global supply chains, persist.

The study is aimed at examining the conditions for the formation of international transport corridors across the Eurasian space and defining the prospects for the participation of countries belonging to the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) in international transport systems for goods movement.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study materials included daily online publications such as Eurasialegal.info, Vedomosti.ru, Ru.sputnik.kg, and others. Additionally, articles published in periodic

scientific journals (e.g., Central Asia and the Caucasus; Economy of Regions; Journal of Transsib Railway Studies; Asia and Africa Today; Transport: Science, Technology, Management; Civil Aviation High Technologies, etc.), as well as regulatory legal documents and transport infrastructure development programs of the EAEU, were used as sources.

Methods employed in the study comprised modeling; assessment of the corridor's development impact on the economic integration of EAEU member states; analysis of the interrelationship between infrastructure projects and trade-economic indicators; visualization of routes, infrastructure facilities, and cargo flows; comparative analysis of international practices.

RESULTS

Globalization has expanded interstate connections in many areas where transport serves as the linking element. The integration of individual states' transport systems into a unified whole enables the formation of an international transport network, which is why the global (including expert) community attributes a particular role to international transport corridors.

A group of experts from the Committee on Inland Transport of the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe has formulated the concept of international transport corridors: "This is a part of a national or international transport system that provides significant international freight and passenger transportation between specific geographical areas. It includes rolling stock and fixed installations of all modes of transport operating in this direction, as well as a set of technological, organizational, and legal conditions for carrying out these transport operations" [24].

The United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) operates with the concept of an "international trade corridor," which is defined as follows: "...a structure of four elements (commercial and financial customs and practices; governmental requirements; infrastructure and equipment; participants) that interact with each other and with their environment to facilitate a country's imports and exports" [25]. The inclusion of these specific elements in the terminology demonstrates the legislative foundation for the application of this concept by individual states, as certain customs and practices are codified in national laws and international treaties. In this context, international transport and trade corridors correlate with each other, at the very least, in their fundamental purpose.

The territories of the EAEU member states are traversed by a network of critical international transport corridors for road and rail communication. These include the Pan-European transport corridors (Crete Corridors), the international transport corridors of the Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific (ESCAP), the railway transport corridors of the Organisation for Cooperation between Railways (OSJD), the corridors of the Central Asian Regional Economic Cooperation (CAREC) program, the "Europe-Western China" corridor, the Trans-Caspian International Transport Route (TITR), and the NSTC.

Given the conceptual references inherent in the term "international trade (transport) corridor", it is necessary to examine the regulatory foundation of Eurasian transport policy.

The Treaty on the Eurasian Economic Union stipulates the implementation of a coordinated transport policy aimed at "...ensuring economic integration, and the consistent, phased formation of a single transport space based on the principles of competition, openness, safety, reliability, accessibility, and environmental sustainability" [26].

This coordinated transport policy within the EAEU is derived from legislatively established priorities, the central one being the creation and development of Eurasian transport corridors.

It should be emphasized that achieving the goals of a balanced transport policy by the EAEU member states cannot be accomplished through prioritization alone. A unified approach is essential, encompassing the formation of a single transport space;

the realization and development of transit potential within the EAEU's customs territory; the coordination of transport infrastructure development; the establishment of logistics centers and transport organizations to optimize carriage processes; the attraction and utilization of member states' human resources potential; the advancement of science and innovation in the transport sector.

In 2023, a Comprehensive Plan for the Development of Eurasian Transport Corridors was developed, slated for implementation both in the short term (2024-2025) and until the set goals are achieved (annually).

The infrastructure of the EAEU member states serves as the key element in organizing the movement of goods and vehicles along Eurasian transport corridors. In turn, the Eurasian Economic Commission (EEC) has issued a recommendation stipulating that

specific requirements for highways must be met by member states for inclusion in the list of Eurasian transport corridors [27].

In order to comply with the established standards, highways must meet the following criteria:

- Be public roads of international, national (republican), and/or private significance;
- Conform to the safety requirements of the Customs Union's Technical Regulation "Safety of Highways" (TR CU 014/2011);
- Possess defined indicators of traffic volume and/or load capacity;
- Occupy a strategically advantageous location;
- Be equipped with automated special technical means (for conducting mandatory types of state control);
- Be provided with necessary service facilities.

The heightened focus on highways within the Eurasian transport agenda is not without purpose. The EAEU has approved a List of Eurasian Transport Corridors and Routes [28], which includes the following section:

1. Eurasian unimodal railway routes.
2. A Eurasian multimodal route.
3. Highways of the EAEU member states included in the Eurasian transport corridors and routes.

A specific feature of the approved Eurasian transport corridors and routes is the predominance of railway and road connections. Nevertheless, waterway cargo transportation between certain territories of the EAEU holds significant promise from the perspective of measurable costs and delivery times, justifying the anticipated expansion of their number. The water segment (from the seaport of Bandar-Anzali, Islamic Republic of Iran, to the seaport of Olya in the Astrakhan region, Russian Federation) is considered one of the most critical arteries for the transport communication of states involved in the implementation of the NSTC. Consequently, the NSTC is regarded as the future of Eurasian logistics.

The Russian Federation has been participating in the functioning of international transport corridors, primarily the Pan-European ones, almost since the proclamation of its sovereignty. The corridor system defined in Crete in 1994 pursued one key objective: to connect European cities (Berlin, Poznan, Warsaw) with Moscow via Minsk (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1 Pan-European transport corridors

Regarding the route connecting the European Union and Russia, the plans of the leadership of the states participating in the Crete project included the expansion of Pan-European Transport Corridor No. 2 and its interconnection with other (European) routes. From the Russian side, this corridor was extended to Nizhny Novgorod and further east, where it connected (via Yekaterinburg) with the Trans-Siberian Railway. This created the prospect of transforming the Pan-European corridor from a European into a Eurasian one. However, political circumstances intervened, causing the mutual transport integration of Europe and Russia to develop slowly, and from 2014, the need for it completely disappeared. Furthermore, Eastern European states and the Russian Federation were not prepared to rapidly modify transport infrastructure and harmonize transport and customs legislation. The phenomenon of multi-vector

divergence also began to emerge – a misalignment in the outcomes of transport route formation, where the European Union sought to focus the Crete Transport Corridor on creating a European transport ring, while Russia, due to its unique geographical position, adhered to a strategy focused on implementing Eurasian transcontinental corridors.

The aforementioned reasons served as an objective basis for the development of the NSTC. Currently, the route from India, Iran, and other countries of Southwest Asia via the Trans-Caspian branch of the NSTC is the most in-demand among existing transport spurs. This fact is corroborated by a growing cargo flow, which Russian ports are struggling to handle fully due to a lack of berths, terminals, cranes, and other infrastructure, particularly in Astrakhan, a small number of vessels on routes linking Iran and Russia, and congestion in the shallowed Volga-Don Canal [29]. Nevertheless, trade turnover via the NSTC has increased by 18% since 2022, with maritime transport volume more than doubling [30].

Eurasian transport infrastructure, including international transport corridors in the East–West and North–South directions, opens opportunities for the EAEU and its member states to connect the markets of Europe, Asia, and the Middle East (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2 North–South international transport corridors [31]

The NSTC implementation, particularly through the involvement of other EAEU member states, will significantly enhance the transit potential of the post-Soviet republics and expand access for their business communities to external markets. The Republic of Armenia and the Republic of Kazakhstan exhibit a high probability of evolving into transit hubs. This is due to Armenia's shared land border with the Islamic Republic of Iran, and Kazakhstan's shared land border with the Russian Federation and a maritime border (via the Caspian Sea) with Iran. The lack of contiguous territory between Russia and Armenia is mitigated by a third transit party – Georgia, connected to Russia by the Georgian Military Road. The Verkhny Lars border crossing point operates at their common border for the movement of goods and vehicles. The remoteness of the Kyrgyz Republic from the NSTC, and crucially, from its key participants (Russia and Iran), prevents this Central Asian republic from extensively engaging in logistics projects associated with the promotion of goods along the NSTC within the EAEU space. Concurrently, Uzbekistan and Kyrgyzstan announced in 2023 the potential use of a Southern Transport Corridor leading to Russia (see Fig. 3).

Figure 3 Southern transport corridor from Kyrgyzstan to Russia [32]

The implementation of this southern route lies through Turkmenistan (the port of Turkmenbashi) to the Astrakhan region of the Russian Federation (the port of Olya) [33]. The advantages of this transportation method for Kyrgyzstan consist of reduced cargo delivery times, allowing it to bypass obstacles at the border between the Kyrgyz Republic and the Republic of Kazakhstan. This apparent benefit for the Kyrgyz side is confronted by an equally obvious contradiction – the absence of a project (or roadmap) for developing a logistics route for the movement of goods and vehicles from Kyrgyzstan to other Central Asian countries. Consequently, while modernizing transport infrastructure and constructing new cargo delivery methods across states participating in transport and logistics projects on the Eurasian space is a viable activity and a forward-looking way to maintain close economic relations, the functionality of any link within the established and operating Eurasian transport system can be instantly disrupted depending on the prevailing political climate. Such a disruption could subsequently lead to the disintegration of established conditions for conducting foreign trade among partner states.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Thus, the prospects of the NSTC within the context of the EAEU's economic integration projects are intrinsically linked to its potential to become a key transport and logistics nexus within the Eurasian Economic Union. The corridor's implementation fosters enhanced economic integration among participating states, optimization of transport infrastructure, and a reduction in costs associated with international freight transport [34–36]. This undertaking exerts a positive influence on the development of foreign trade, attracts investment, and facilitates the realization of joint projects, thereby bolstering the global market competitiveness of the EAEU. In the context of geopolitical shifts and the imperative to diversify trade routes, the NSTC can serve as a crucial factor in strengthening economic stability and integration processes among the Union's member states, as well as expanding cooperation in the spheres of transport, logistics, and infrastructure projects.

Summarizing the above, the following conclusions can be drawn. The EAEU member states play a pivotal role in organizing cargo movement along the NSTC, as the Russian Federation and other post-Soviet nations are currently the primary shapers of the Eurasian economic integration agenda. Facilitating connections between the northern and southern regions of Eurasia promotes the development of foreign trade relations and international economic cooperation, streamlines the foundation

of transport logistics, and enhances the efficiency of transport infrastructure. The transition from the normative formalization of steps for implementing Eurasian transport corridors to the adoption of a unified mechanism (or mechanisms) for the direct operation of international logistics routes within the EAEU member states should mark a new phase in advancing the goals of sustainable (economic) development across the entire Eurasian region.

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